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Research Article

**A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL TO DETERMINE
THE EFFICACY OF 0.9% SALINE VS HYPERTONIC (3%)
SALINE FOR ACUTE VIRAL BRONCHIOLITIS**Dr Ahmad Zaki¹, Dr Zainab Riaz², Sonia Rehman Orakzai³¹MBBS, Khyber Medical University, Peshawar²WMO in Anaesthesia Department at DHQ Hospital, Dera Ghazi Khan³Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To compare the length of hospital stay (primary) and improvement of clinical (secondary) severity indices in children with bronchiolitis nebulized with 3% hypertonic saline or 0.9% saline.

Design: Randomized double-blind controlled trial.

Place and Duration: In the Pediatric department of Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar for six-months duration from January 2020 to July 2020.

Methods: Hospitalized children (1-24 months) with moderate acute bronchiolitis were included. Nebulize 4 ml of 3% hypertonic saline or 4 ml of 0.9% saline with 2.5 mg of salbutamol at 4-hour intervals until the patient is ready for discharge.

Results: Baseline characteristics were similar in the two groups. The median clinical grade on admission was 6 (IQR-1) in both groups. Clinical severity markers monitored 12 hours to discharge (132 hours) showed no statistically significant differences in the 3% and 0.9% salt groups. The mean hospital stay (time to the predefined clinical severity score <3) was 63.93 ± 22.43 h in the 3% saline group and 63.51 ± 21.27 h in the 0.9% saline group (P = 0.878). In both groups, no adverse events were reported by parents, or healthcare professionals.

Conclusion: Nebulized 3% saline does not exceed 0.9% saline in infants with clinically diagnosed acute bronchiolitis.

Key words: nebulization with 3% saline, bronchiolitis, management

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INTRODUCTION:

Viral bronchiolitis is a common cause of hospitalization of infants and contributes to an enormous economic burden. Generally, bronchiolitis is seasonal with peak hospitalization between 3 and 6 months of age. Standard treatment remains supportive care and includes ensuring adequate oxygen exchange, fluid intake, and feeding the baby¹⁻². Meta-analyses of data on the most commonly used treatments for acute bronchiolitis, namely nebulized bronchodilators, epinephrine, glucocorticosteroids, and thoracic physiotherapy, showed no significant effect on clinical outcomes compared to placebo, except for some benefit of adrenaline compared to placebo in case of timely results for outpatients, especially in the first 24 hours of care³⁻⁴. Current clinical practice guidelines do not recommend the routine use of any medications, but despite evidence, the use of ineffective treatments for bronchiolitis remains high. Recently, several researchers have reported the use of hypertonic saline in infants with bronchiolitis, which has resulted in significant treatment benefits, many of which have reported. It has been reported to positively influence mucociliary clearance in both healthy and diseased lungs in a number of clinical situations, including bronchiolitis⁵⁻⁶. This method has enormous cost-saving potential in both developing and developed countries, even more so if it could actually reduce hospital admissions, a recent Cochrane review suggests⁷⁻⁸. Therefore, on the basis of the available literature, we hypothesized that a 3% hypertonic saline solution would reduce hospital stay compared to 0.9% saline in patients with bronchiolitis. We conducted this study to evaluate the effectiveness of nebulized 3% hypertonic saline in children diagnosed with clinical bronchiolitis.

METHOD:

We designed a randomized, double-blind, controlled study in infants and children aged 1 to 24 months hospitalized with moderate acute bronchiolitis in the Pediatric department of Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar for six-months duration from January 2020 to July 2020. Children with clinical symptoms of viral bronchiolitis and hospitalized with a clinical severity of 3-6 were included. Bronchiolitis was defined as the first episode of wheezing along with prodromal symptoms of upper respiratory tract infection, including rhinorrhea, cough, and sometimes a low fever that may progress to dyspnea. Children with impaired consciousness, heart disease, chronic respiratory diseases, prior episode of wheezing, progressive respiratory failure requiring respiratory support other than oxygen administration were excluded. Subjects who had received nebulized hypertonic saline in the last 12 hours were also

excluded. Our hospital's institutional ethics committee approved the study. Signed informed consent was obtained from the parents of all children. All patients were admitted within 24 hours of being admitted to hospital. Computer generated random numbers were used for subsequent recruitments and patients were randomized to nebulize 4 ml of 3% hypertonic saline or 4 ml of 0.9% saline along with 2.5 mg of salbutamol at 4-hour intervals, six times a day for patient. was ready for discharge. There was no detectable difference in color, odor or other physical properties between the 0.9% saline solution and the 3% hypertonic saline solution. The combination code of the treatment package (0.9% saline vs.3% hypertonic saline) was not available to the researcher or medical staff. The code has been deposited with the statistics. We used a conventional jet nebulizer with a fitted face mask connected to a pressurized oxygen supply set at a flow rate of 7 L / min through a tight-fitting face mask. Nebulization continued until the nebulization chamber was empty. Patients were examined by the investigators at the start of the study and daily. Monitoring parameters for improvement or deterioration were measured and recorded on admission, and then at 12-hour intervals using the clinical assessment described by Wang et al. Discharge criteria were good oral nutrition, no need for IV fluids and supplemental oxygen, clinical severity ≤ 3 , no use of an extra muscle or rapid breathing (respiration rate < 31 bpm) and oxygen saturation $> 92\%$ in air. We measured the length of hospital stay from admission to clinical score < 3 . Statistical analysis: The primary focus of interest was to compare length of hospital stay (time to achieve clinical severity score < 3), and the secondary goal was to compare improvement in clinical severity scores in children hospitalized with acute bronchiolitis nebulized with 3% hypertonic saline and normal saline. Previously, it was proposed that reducing hospital stay by 1 day as clinically relevant. This was expected to require a sample of 113 patients per arm. This number was based on the mean pre-study stay in hospital of 3.5 ± 2.9 days. Each variable was scanned for normal distribution. Categorical variables were compared using the Chi-square test. All continuous variables were compared using paired or unpaired t-test, respectively. A p value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. To test clinical severity ratings at 12-hour intervals, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was performed on each treatment group separately. In this analysis, a p value of 0.005 was considered significant due to multiple comparisons.

RESULTS:

The study was conducted among 277 potentially eligible patients with a clinical diagnosis of bronchiolitis were admitted, of which 248

successfully completed the protocol (Fig. 1). Both study groups had similar baseline characteristics (Table I) including age, gender, and clinical severity scores.

TABLE I BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDY SUBJECTS

Characteristics	Hypertonic saline	Normal saline
	N=125	N=123
Age, mo (mean)	4.93 ± 4.31	4.18±4.24
No. of patients in different age groups		
1-6 mo	93	105
7-12 mo	24	13
12-24 mo	8	5
Male/female (n)	97/28	92/31
Duration of symptoms* (d)	3.6±2.87	3.8±2.34
Baseline O ₂ saturation%	94.43±2.77	95.23±2.45
Mean time (h) [#]	8.6±4.63	9.1±7.62
Clinical score [^] (median)	6	6

Clinical severity assessments monitored every 12 hours until discharge (132 hours) showed no statistically significant differences between the two groups (Fig. 2). However, it should be noted that the median clinical severity at time 0 would be based on 125 subjects, while the data at 132 hours would be based on only 2 patients. There was no difference in the mean length of hospital stay in the 0.9% saline (63.93 ± 22.43 hours) and 3% hypertonic saline (63.51 ± 21.27) groups (p = 0.878). The percentage of patients who remained in each group at 24-hour intervals is shown in Fig. 3. Parents, guardians or treating health professionals in both groups did not report any adverse events related to nebulized treatment.

FIG.1 Participant flow diagram.

FIG. 2 Median clinical severity score of two groups at 12-hourly intervals.

FIG.3 Patients remaining in each group at 24-h intervals.

DISCUSSION:

Ours is one of the largest studies comparing nebulization of 3% hypertonic saline and 0.9% (normal) saline in hospitalized children with acute bronchiolitis. However, both groups were comparable in terms of baseline characteristics; we found no advantage of hypertonic (3%) saline over normal (0.9%) saline in terms of length of hospital stay and clinical severity score monitored from admission to discharge. Shorter hospital stays and lower admission rates were established as an objective and clinically relevant measure of profitability⁹⁻¹⁰. A Cochrane meta-analysis (four studies) reported a 24.1% shorter (mean 1.16 days, 95% CI -1.55 to -0.77 days) hospital stay with hypertonic saline. However, one of these studies, which showed a maximum reduction (-1.4 days) of hypertonic saline, had a longer stay (almost twice as long as in the other 3 studies) in both groups, leading to heterogeneity in the data. Khalid et al. they recently reported a shorter stay with hypertonic saline, but when we look at the actual length of hospital stay in different groups, there is only a difference of a few hours which may not be clinically meaningful. The 7 days post-discharge revision rate was also similar in all groups in their study, reflecting the lack of superiority of hypertonic saline. The average length of hospital stay in our study was similar at 3%, and normal saline was similar, but shorter in both groups compared to all other researchers. Most emergency or outpatient studies did not show any significant advantage of hypertonic saline over normal saline in improving clinical severity or hospitalization rates. However, studies in hospitalized bronchiolitis patients showed better improvement in clinical severity scores with hypertonic saline, but the degree of improvement varied between treatment days, ranging from 15.7% on Day 1 to 29.4% on Day 1. 3rd day in the hypertonic saline group¹¹. Concentration-dependent improvement (normal saline <3% saline <5% saline) in the clinical severity rating described by Khalid et

al. Was measured immediately after nebulization, but the transient improvement may not have an impact on length of hospitalization. We found no significant difference in the CS scores at enrollment and thereafter at 12-hour intervals until discharge in both groups. Sood et al. showed that an increase in airway surface fluid volume is associated with an increased muco-ciliary clearance rate in healthy subjects¹²⁻¹³. It turned out that the change in fluid depth on the airway surface after inhalation of saline or hypertonic saline is a function of the NaCl mass added to the airway surface by aerosols with different NaCl concentrations. The ceiling effect of higher inhaled NaCl could be a possible reason why any difference between hypertonic saline and normal saline could not be documented in our study. We did not have a placebo group for ethical reasons because the only placebo for nebulization therapy may be NS, which is itself a treatment method. We did not attempt virological diagnostics because we did not have a facility. While this is a real clinical scenario for the treatment of bronchiolitis in developing countries, given the age limit, we could enroll several children with a diagnosis other than bronchiolitis¹⁴⁻¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, nebulized 3% hypertonic saline does not exceed 0.9% saline in infants and children with clinically diagnosed acute bronchiolitis (without RSV confirmation). Further large-scale studies are needed to prove its clinical benefits before its routine use in patients with acute viral bronchiolitis is recommended.

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